

Data and Cloud Polymorphic Application Modelling in Multi-clouds and Fog Environments*

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Abstract. Multi-cloud management prevents vendor lock-in as well as improves the provisioning of cloud applications. However, the optimal deployment of such applications is still impossible, not only due to the dynamicity of the cloud and hybrid environments that host these applications but also due to the use of potentially unsuitable forms or configurations of application components. As such, the real cloud application optimisation can only be achieved by considering all possible component forms and selecting the best one, based on both application requirements and the current context. This gives rise to the era of polymorphic applications which can change form at runtime based on their context. A major prerequisite for the management of such applications is their proper modelling. Therefore, this paper presents extensions on two well-integrated cloud modelling solutions to support the complete specification of polymorphic applications and it presents an illustrative example of their use.

Keywords: polymorphic, application, multi-cloud, modelling, language.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, an abundance of cloud service offerings is obtainable and rapidly adopted by enterprises based on their preeminence to traditional computing models [1]. However, at the same time, the computing requirements of modern cloud applications have been exponentially increased due to available big data that require processing [2], [3]. The emergence of data-intensive applications necessitated the wide adoption of multi-cloud deployment models, to vest on all cloud computing advantages without any restriction on who is the cloud service provider [3]. Considering different application forms, based on current needs or available infrastructural offers near the data sources, is also a significant challenge for multi-cloud management platforms (MCMPs).

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We refer to polymorphic applications, i.e., applications that can have alternative architecture variants, derived from the different application components forms (e.g., function or micro-service) or configuration styles (VM, serverless). As such, each architecture variant maps to selecting one form of each component from those possible. Thus, depending on the application requirements, one architecture variant can be selected and deployed in a single cloud or across multiple ones or even fog environments. So, the main research issues involved are: (a) how to automatically select and deploy the right architecture variant; (b) how to adapt both the application architecture variant and its configuration, based on current application requirements and context. The benefits of addressing these research issues are considerable since the application deployment always optimally satisfies the current requirements and context, leading to a reliable service level delivery, the increase of application and its provider reputation and the subsequent increase of provider's net gain. So, polymorphic applications tend to change the research map of multi-cloud application management [1].

A major pre-requisite to support polymorphic application management in multi-clouds is polymorphic application modelling. Without the proper modelling of polymorphic applications, their optimal deployment and reconfiguration cannot be supported by any MCMP. Thus, this modelling kind not only needs to be rich enough but should deeply cover all necessary management domains, including deployment, requirements and monitoring. To the best of our knowledge, no other related approach can supply such a support. We elaborate more on this in section 2 to argue that currently no cloud modelling language can satisfy all the aspects of polymorphic application modelling. This shortcoming is also affirmed by the fact that currently there are not any MCMPs that can automatically support application polymorphism at runtime. This is true both for research platforms in the cloud domain but also well-established tools (e.g., Kubernetes). As such, in this work, we discuss extensions over our previous work on application modelling for multi-clouds, using the Cloud Application Modelling and Execution Language (CAMEL) [2] and the Metadata Schema (MDS) [3] so as to sufficiently support the modelling of polymorphic applications.

CAMEL is a rich modelling language covering all necessary domains for multi-cloud application management. However, it currently lacks the necessary conceptual capabilities to support polymorphic application specification as it is not able to model all possible application component forms and configurations. Further, it misses other heterogeneous resources (e.g., accelerators, edge resources) and network-related concepts. As such, this work discusses the extensions conducted in CAMEL to deliver the missing polymorphic application modelling capabilities.

MDS is also a rich metadata schema covering concepts and their relations across the application deployment, big data management and contextual security domains. It includes concepts and properties related to where (big data) applications should be placed, how big data can be actually managed and how access to both data and resources (including application components) can be restricted. Such a schema is quite handy in the context of extending CAMEL at the model level plus supplying suitable annotations for CAMEL elements at the same level. As such, CAMEL is enhanced to describe additional features or domains (e.g., requirements for resources like Virtual Machines (VMs) and Graphical Processing Units (GPUs)) without the need to extend

it at the conceptual level. However, after carefully examining the application deployment domain, MDS was found to lack some important concepts related to specific resource kinds (e.g., High-Performance Computing (HPC), hardware-accelerated ones), platform kinds (e.g., serverless) and network elements. Further, some small gaps (e.g., missing trusted execution environment concepts) were also identified in terms of the other two domains (i.e., big data management and contextual security). Thus, in the context of supporting polymorphic application modelling and annotation, MDS has been also extended to cover all missing conceptual elements.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses relevant work on cloud application modelling. Section 3 presents CAMEL and its extensions towards polymorphic application modelling, while it also discusses its enhancement via MDS. Section 4 focuses on the new aspects that were appended to MDS so as to offer a complete and formal vocabulary of concepts and properties for describing cloud service offerings. Section 5 showcases the capabilities of this application modelling approach in a real 5G cloud-RAN application. The last section finally concludes this work and discusses future directions with respect to cloud application modelling.

2 Related Work

2.1 Cloud Application Modelling Languages

This section assesses whether the cloud (application) modelling languages (CMLs) support both multi-cloud and polymorphic application modelling. To assess all relevant cloud application and service modelling languages, we rely on the criteria framework in [2] that we extend to cover the polymorphic modelling aspect. This framework includes the following evaluation criteria: i) *domain coverage*: which domains relevant to the application lifecycle are covered; ii) *integration level*: what is the level of integration [2] between the different domains/sub-languages covered/utilized; iii) *delivery model support*: which kinds of cloud services are supported; iv) *models@runtime*: for which domains is models@runtime paradigm [4] adopted.

A CML supports polymorphic modelling when it satisfies the following criteria: i) *application architecture variability*: a CML can capture different forms of application components and thus cover the different variations of an application architecture. This criterion is evaluated as “low” when the CML does not support modelling component forms, “medium” when it indirectly supports this, or “high”, otherwise. ii) *component configuration variability*: the CML can capture any kind of component configuration, such as script, container, serverless and accelerated resource configurations. Thus, the higher is the number of different configuration kinds captured, the better is the CML. This criterion is evaluated as “low” when the CML supports one or two configuration kinds, “medium” when it supports three to four kinds, or “high” otherwise. iii) *component complexity*: application components in one form can be standalone and composite in another. Thus, a CML should support the modelling of both component kinds. This criterion is evaluated as “low” when a CML does not make explicit the distinction of

single and complex components, “medium” when it makes this distinction but not properly models complex components, or “high” otherwise.

Based on the enhanced criteria framework, we have analysed 13 provider-independent CMLs (see Table 1), including CAMEL, as provider-independence is a crucial feature to support cross- and multi-cloud application deployments. As can be seen, CAMEL 2.0 was already above competition due to its domain coverage, integration level, cloud service type coverage and models@runtime support for the deployment, monitoring and data domains. CAMEL 3.0 builds on CAMEL 2.0 so as to enhance it with polymorphic modelling capabilities. Thus, CAMEL 3.0 advances the state-of-the-art in both multi-cloud and polymorphic application modelling.

From the rest of the CMLs, we can distinguish three languages, which exhibit better performance in different criteria clusters. TOSCA is a standard widely used in research able to cover two kinds of cloud services while its ongoing extension will support the models@runtime paradigm for the deployment domain. However, in terms of domain coverage, this CML seems to focus mainly on the deployment domain and slightly on the requirement one. TOSCA has a medium component configuration variability due to its ability to support some but not all configuration kinds. However, the latter support is not exactly implanted in TOSCA syntax as in CAMEL.

ModaCloudML can be discerned due to its polymorphic modelling support which is close but not equal to that of CAMEL 2.0. In particular, this CML seems to support some of the possible component configuration kinds while it caters for component complexity: it allows specifying composite components through their constituent components but does not fully explicate their internal deployment model.

StratusML can be distinguished from ModaCloudML & TOSCA based on its domain coverage and integration level, where the latter is due to its homogenous way to model different domains. However, the domain coverage is not as extensive and deep as in CAMEL. Further, no polymorphic modelling capabilities exist in that language.

Table 1. Evaluation of Cloud Application Modelling Languages.

DSL	Dom. Cover.	Integr. Level	Deliv. Model Supp.	models@runtime	App. Arch. Var.	Comp. Conf. Var.	Comp. Compl.
Vamp [5]	low	N/A	IaaS	N/A	low	low	low
4CaaS Template [6]	low	N/A	IaaS, PaaS	N/A	low	low	low
TOSCA [7]	medium	medium	IaaS, PaaS	deployment	low	medium	low
GENTL [8]	low	N/A	IaaS	N/A	low	low	low
ModaCloudML [9]	medium	low	IaaS, PaaS	deployment	low	medium	medium
CAML [10]	medium	medium	IaaS	N/A	low	low	low
StratusML [11]	medium	high	IaaS	deployment	low	low	low
CAMEL 2.0	high	high	IaaS, PaaS, SaaS	deployment, metric, data	medium	medium	medium

CAMEL 3.0	high	high	IaaS, PaaS, SaaS	deployment, metric, data	me- dium	high	high
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2.2 Ontologies and Metadata for Cloud Application & Services Description

Next, we highlight all approaches consulted to extend MDS so as to completely cover all possible resource and platform kinds. As MDS already covers well the big data domain and supplies adequate support for common resource types and services [3], the analysis focuses on the network and hardware-accelerator domains, i.e., the two most significant MDS extensions.

Network Domain. In [12] a meta-model for cyber-physical systems is suggested, mainly focusing on their communication. [13] proposes a network description language specialised in describing network topologies for hybrid networks. The ToCo ontology [14] can specify the physical infrastructure as well as the quality of channel, services and users in heterogeneous, multi-domain telecommunication networks. The ontology in [15] enables to specify telecommunication services, to easily discover them plus address the semantic interoperability problem.

Hardware Accelerator Domain. [16] suggests a modular and extensible XML-based platform language able to specify heterogeneous multicore systems and clusters at both the hardware and software level. OMG's MARTE [17] enables specifying hardware architectures. It includes the GRM meta-model, able to describe various resource types like storage, communication, computing and device, as well as the HRM meta-model spanning two views: logical that classifies each hardware resource based on its functional properties while covering various concrete resources of multiple resource types and the physical view focusing on the resources' physical properties. The CloudLightning ontology [18] facilitates the incorporation of heterogeneous resources and HPC environments in the Cloud. It provides support for resource management by modelling hardware accelerators as well as different resource abstraction methods and intelligently matching service requests to heterogeneous infrastructures.

3 CAMEL

3.1 Introduction to CAMEL

CAMEL is a multi-domain-specific language (multi-DSL) enabling to specify provider-independent, multi-cloud applications. CAMEL covers well all relevant domains in the application lifecycle via its respective DSLs. These DSLs have been developed to map to the same level of expressiveness while they have been properly integrated to avoid various modelling discrepancies, like the duplication of information [2]. Further, these DSLs are assorted with rules which cover the semantic and syntactic validation of models conforming to them within and across domains. CAMEL conforms to the `models@runtime` paradigm. In particular, devops users specify domain (e.g.,

deployment) models at the type-level which are then exploited by the MCMP to drive the deployment and management of the respective application. During such exploitation, the MCMP produces and maintains domain models at the instance level which reflect the current application state in the respective domains. The production of the sub-models of an application’s CAMEL model is facilitated by the use of a textual-based CAMEL editor, generated via Eclipse Xtext². This editor enables the rapid, user-intuitive editing of CAMEL models as it exhibits various features, such as error and syntax highlighting, syntax completion and hove-over documentation-based assistance. Complementary, the devops can consult the online CAMEL documentation³ for further assistance.

Fig. 1. The cloud application management process and CAMEL without (left figure) and with polymorphic capabilities (right figure)

Fig. 1 (left part) depicts the way CAMEL models are exploited and evolved by a MCMP. Initially, the DevOps supplies a *provided-independent model* of her application. The MCMP then via deployment reasoning produces a *provider-specific model*. Next, this model is exploited to orchestrate the application deployment. Finally, while the application executes, relevant execution facts are fed into the application’s execution sub-model, giving rise to a CAMEL *execution model*. Such facts are exploited to optimally reconfigure the application to close the application’s optimisation loop.

3.2 Enhancing CAMEL through MDS

The application placement domain includes other domains like the resource and platform ones. Such domains are in constant change due to the introduction of new technologies resulting in new resource and platform kinds. This creates the need to extend existing CMLs at the language level to enable the modelling of elements or models relevant to these new kinds. However, such an extension is conducted by either enhancing existing meta-models or modelling and incorporating new ones with the same formalism. This increases the modelling effort, introduces unnecessary restrictions in

² <https://www.eclipse.org/Xtext/>

³ <http://camel-dsl.org/documentation/>

modelling such domains while makes CMLs quite complex. Thus, this increases their learning curve and decreases their usability. Another alternative is to allow for a generic description of any domain such that each domain can be extended at will. This, however, means that the semantics of each domain is not precisely captured. As a result, the respective CML becomes hard to comprehend and use.

To this end, it was decided to follow a solution that lies in between the two extremes. This relies on the fact that CAMEL 2.0 captures well the core of all domains while an arbitrary structure can be followed for extensions of these domains or their sub-domains. To achieve this, a novel and lightweight mechanism has been introduced in CAMEL 2.0 that plays a dual role: (a) it enables semantically annotating almost any CAMEL element kind to supply precise semantics for them. This can facilitate, e.g., raising the automation in application management; (b) it enables arbitrarily extending CAMEL models. In particular, CAMEL elements can include sub-features and attributes that could enable, e.g., to specify constraints on various kinds of resources or platforms. In this sense, CAMEL does not need to be extended at all at the language level to cover new resource/platform sub-domains.

The mechanism was realised via 2 main extensions while transiting from CAMEL 1.0 to 2.0. First, the introduction of new CAMEL super-concepts, inherited by most of the others. Such super-concepts enable to semantically annotate CAMEL model elements through references to MDS elements as well as to enable an arbitrary structure on a CAMEL element via its potential expansion with feature hierarchies. Second, the introduction of the metadata domain. This enables to codify in CAMEL any conceptual schema (in any kind of form like an ontology or taxonomy), including the MDS.

The benefits from introducing the above mechanism are numerous. First, CAMEL can be re-used in different MCMPs, if such MCMPs have already decided to rely on a certain schema. Second, CAMEL can be extended at the model level to cover new resource and platform sub-domains. As such, CAMEL model specifications can be quite rich, incorporating constraints on, e.g., various kinds of hardware-accelerated resources like GPUs and FPGAs. An example of how MDS is used in CAMEL is provided in Section 5 code excerpts where certain modelling artefacts are annotated with a prefix following the pattern “*MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema*”.

3.3 CAMEL v3.0

CAMEL 3.0 was designed based on specific requirements, which relate to CAMEL’s improvement feedback collected from past European projects [2], the realisation of the polymorphic modelling capability and some generic requirements from real use-cases. These requirements can be summarised as follows (where *PM* means polymorphic-related, *IR* improvement related, and *UC* use-case related): i) *PM1*: New configurations for components have to be covered, especially those related to hardware-acceleration-use scenarios; ii) *PM2*: Each component configuration may come with its own requirement set with respect to, e.g., the resources or the environment on top of them; iii) *PM3*: Components, depending on their form, can be either standalone or complex. For example, a component managing users could be either offered as a micro-service or as a composite component comprising a set of serverless functions; iv) *IR1*: Components

should be re-used in the context of different applications to reduce both the application modelling and development time; v) UC1: Communication requirements must be expressed as constraints on the quality of the communication (e.g., latency) between two application components. Such constraints deliver flexibility in the deployment of the component pair.

All these requirements led to extending existing CAMEL domains with some missing concepts and relations. The main rationale for such an extension was that the communication aspect was neglected in CAMEL 2.0 while the polymorphic modelling support had to be improved mainly on the deployment domain. The communication-related changes (UC1) led to introducing *CommunicationRequirement*, a feature-based kind of requirement over the quality of communication between components, *CommunicationMeasurement*, a measurement related to communication quality, as well as updating monitoring related concepts like *ObjectContext* (such that the object being measured can be also a communication). The latter change enables to specify communication related metrics and SLOs which can then be evaluated and possibly lead to the application reconfiguration at runtime.

Fig. 2. The deployment domain in CAMEL

Concerning the deployment domain, new component configuration kinds were introduced (PM1), covering hardware-accelerated scenarios, while each configuration is now associated with its own requirement set (PM2). Further, a new concept was incorporated called *PolymorphicModel*, representing a provider-independent polymorphic application deployment architecture that covers all deployment architecture variants, which can be produced by selecting one from all possible configurations per each component (and be modelled via a *DeploymentTypeModel*). Finally, component complexity was catered by associating a composite component with its own internal polymorphic model (PM3). This enables component re-use in the sense that composite components

can be regarded as individual applications on their own or can be exploited to build more complex applications (IR1). In Fig. 2 we depict a UML class diagram that covers the modelling in this domain.

Apart from evolving CAMEL, the polymorphic application modelling has extended the deployment reasoning activity (see Fig. 1 - right part). As first, the right application architecture variant needs to be selected and then the right cloud providers and resources need to be selected to provide support to the selected component configurations. The input to the first reasoning activity is named as *polymorphic model* while its result is the *provider-independent model* (see *DeploymentModelType* class), i.e., the input to the original deployment reasoning activity, now second in order.

4 Metadata Schema

4.1 Overview of MDS

This section introduces an extensive update of the vocabulary entitled *Metadata Schema* (MDS) [3] which aggregates a number of concepts and properties to support describing requirements, constraints and offerings' characteristics in multi-cloud placement decisions. The structured description of these characteristics constitutes the formal means for extending CAMEL with appropriate concepts related to big data management, application component placement and access control in multi-cloud environments. In this respect, MDS comprises the *Application Placement*, *Big Data* and *Context Aware Security* models that group a number of classes and properties as it is depicted in Fig. 3 which unveils MDS top-level classes.

Fig. 3. Metadata Schema overview

In this work, MDS is enhanced to cover the desired abstraction constructs, which will be used in CAMEL to model polymorphic applications, regarding the areas of data management, polymorphic application design plus the use of heterogeneous resources (including HPC resources, accelerators) and platforms (including serverless). Besides the above aspects, the extensions involve network related aspects that should drive or

affect the cloud application deployment. Due to space limitations, we now supply for each MDS extension a short description along with a fine-grained depiction of its UML class diagram, which also shows the value types of object and data properties. A complete view in the form of a high-resolution image of the complete MDS taxonomy can be found here⁴.

4.2 MDS Extensions

In the first version of MDS, the *Processing* class (a subclass of *Application Placement Model/IaaS*) involved only the *RAM*, *CPU* and *GPU* subclasses. Fig. 4 supplies a fine-grained view of MDS updates, regarding the *Processing* class, involving any infrastructural feature bound to the processing capability of virtualised resources. Classes *Processing*, *CPU* and *Memory* were enriched with extra properties (e.g., *hasCacheType*, *hasBlockSize* regarding *CacheStructure*, *hasReplicationPolicy* etc.), while new classes were added (e.g., *HPC*, *ASIC*, *VPU* etc.) as it is explained below.

Fig. 4. Part of the UML class diagram for the Processing domain

Specifically, *HPC* and *Accelerator* classes were introduced. *HPC* refers to the high performance features provided by the computing platform which can boost the overall

⁴ <https://melodic.cloud/UuTf-KRW.png>

application performance. The *Accelerator* class refers to application-specific hardware designed or programmed to compute operations faster than a general-purpose computer processor. It involves the following main subclasses: i) *GPU* which refers to IaaS resources that use graphics processing units (GPUs), i.e., specialized electronic circuits initially designed to rapidly manipulate memory to accelerate the creation of images in a frame buffer; ii) *ASIC* referring to application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs), an accelerator category that employs strategies like optimised memory and use of lower precision arithmetic, to accelerate calculation and increase computation throughput; iii) *VPU* which refers to the vision processing unit (VPU), a category of microprocessors intended to accelerate machine vision algorithms and tasks; iv) *FPGA*: refers to IaaS resources that use field programmable gate arrays (FPGAs), as integrated circuits made to be configured by the user after manufacturing.

Another important IaaS subclass introduced is the *NetworkEntity* representing any kind of network entity that could be included in a Cloud. Several properties and subclasses have been added to cover all the network-related elements that can be considered for managing applications hosted over multi-clouds and fog computing environments. The main subclasses of the *NetworkEntity* class are the following: i) *Network* which refers to the network related aspects that bind the operation and communication capabilities of an offered or a requested (Fog) IaaS resource; ii) *NetworkQoS* that represents the main aspects of the network quality of service; iii) *SoftwareNetworkEntity* that represents a software-based network entity; iv) *HardwareNetworkEntity*: refers to all aspects of hardware-based network entities that may constitute network nodes serving the cloud application components.

Fig. 5. UML class diagram showing the serverless class hierarchy.

The *PaaS class* encapsulates all attributes related to platform level cloud resources required and offered for deploying multi-cloud applications. The main addition is its new *Serverless* subclass that represents all serverless platform-as-a-service (PaaS) aspects that enable the deployment of functions/serverless components in the cloud. The main subclasses of the *Serverless* class (see also Fig. 5) are the following: i) *Composition*: represents the technology used to support function composition; ii) *Cost*: represents the cost model of a serverless PaaS; iii) *FreeQuota*: concerns the free quota per month for a serverless PaaS account; iv) *Limits*: represents the set of limitations that are associated with a serverless PaaS.

The platform level also involved extensions in the *Security Controls* class. Specifically, the subclasses *SecurityConfiguration* and *HardwareBasedSecurity* were introduced. The first refers to all configuration aspects over a network entity, specified via a network access rule set (defined as a separate subclass called *NetworkAccessRule*). The latter aggregates all security capabilities offered as a service by dedicated hardware components. The *HardwareBasedSecurity* subclasses are: i) *FPGA Security*: refers to security capabilities implanted in a FPGA hardware; ii) *SecureEnclave* which refers to the capability of a trusted execution environment based on dedicated microkernels that support isolation and encryption.

Also, a number of important extensions were introduced in MDS Big-Data Model. For example, the *Data Management* class of the *Big-Data Model* was extended. It encapsulates all relevant concepts enabling to describe major technological choices with respect to how big data is acquired, stored, processed, transferred or replicated for redundancy reasons. The extensions involve both new subclasses and properties.

5 Modelling a 5G cloud-RAN Application

This section involves the modelling of a real application in the 5G Software-defined Radio Access Networks (RAN) domain mapping to a use-case of the Morphemic project (www.morphemic.cloud) provided by use-case partner IS-Wireless (www.is-wireless.com). Such a modelling, covering CAMEL 3.0 & MDS extensions, relates to the basic use-case scenario of cloud deployment with one optimisation objective, specific communication requirements and components with multiple configurations.

A RAN system comprises various protocols like radio-frequency (RF) and the physical one. Many such protocols can be virtualised and grouped in the form of components: the Distributed Unit (DU) one comprising intermediate-level protocols and the Central Unit (CU) one comprising high-level protocols. The CU unit can be also separated into the control (CP) and user plane (UP) such that the respective parts, i.e., CU-CP and CU-UP, can be independently deployed.

For the static deployment scenario, various kinds of requirements have been considered. The generic requirements are the following: i) the location of all components should be in Poland; ii) each component must have at least 2 GBs of RAM; iii) script-based configurations for components require at least 5 number of cores; iv) the application average availability should be at least 99.999%; v) the overall average response time should be minimised. The communication-specific requirements are the following: i) DU ↔ CU-CP: 5 ms latency and 0.4 Gbps throughput; ii) DU ↔ CU-UP: 1 ms latency and 4 Gbps throughput. Finally, FPGA-specific requirements are given for the CU-CP component: i) Total memory should be at least 2430 Kb; ii) Number of logic elements should be at least 145000.

```

camel model Network5G {
  polymorphic model Network5gAppModel {
    global requirements GlobalReqs
    requirements GlobalReqs {
      resource ReqModel.RES location ReqModel.PL
    }
    requirements ScriptReqs {
      resource ReqModel.RES1
    }
    requirements FPGAReqs {
      resource ReqModel.RES2
    }
    component DU {
      provided port prov_DU_CU_CP port 1111 provided port prov_DU_CU_UP port 1113
      required port req_CU_CP_DU port 1112 required port req_CU_UP_DU port 1114
      script configuration DU_Script_Config {
        download "xxx" install "yyy" configure "zzz" reqScriptReqs
      }
    }
    component CU_CP {
      provided port prov_CU_CP_DU port 1112 required port req_DU_CU_CP port 1111
      script configuration CU_CP_Script_Config {
        download "xxx" install "yyy" configure "zzz" reqFPGAReqs
      }
    }
    serverless configuration CU_CP_Servi_Config {
      binary code URL "xxx"
    }
  }
  component CU_UP {
    provided port prov_CU_UP_DU port 1114 required port req_DU_CU_UP port 1113
    script configuration CU_UP_Script_Config {
      download "xxx" install "yyy" configure "zzz" reqScriptReqs
    }
  }
  communication DU_CU_CP from CU_CP.req_DU_CU_CP to DU.prov_DU_CU_CP req
  ReqModel.DU_CU_CP_COMREQ
  communication CU_CP_DU from DU.req_CU_CP_DU to CU_CP.prov_CU_CP_DU req
  ReqModel.CU_CP_COMREQ
  communication DU_CU_UP from CU_UP.req_DU_CU_UP to DU.prov_DU_CU_UP req
  ReqModel.DU_CU_UP_COMREQ
  communication CU_UP_DU from DU.req_CU_UP_DU to CU_UP.prov_CU_UP_DU req
  ReqModel.CU_UP_COMREQ
}

```

Fig. 6. The 5G RAN use case polymorphic model

```

requirement model ReqModel {
  link requirement DU_CU_CP_COMREQ {
    attribute Throughput
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Network
    Entity.Network.NetworkQoS.hasTxput] : double 0.1
    attribute Latency
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Network
    Entity.Network.NetworkQoS.hasLatency] : double 5.0
  }
  link requirement DU_CU_UP_COMREQ {
    attribute Throughput
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Network
    Entity.Network.NetworkQoS.hasTxput] : double 4.0
    attribute Latency
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Network
    Entity.Network.NetworkQoS.hasLatency] : double 1.0
  }
  resource requirement RES {
    attribute RAM
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Cloud.V
    MFlavor.hasRAM] : int 2 UnitTemplate.UnitModel.GigaBytes
  }
  resource requirement RES1 {
    attribute CORES
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Processi
    ng.CPU.hasMinNumberofCores] : int 5
  }
  resource requirement RES2 {
    attribute CORES
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Processi
    ng.CPU.hasMinNumberofCores] : int 5
    attribute TOTAL_MEM
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Processing.A
    ccelerator.FPGA.FPGAMemory.hasTotalMemory] : int 4230 UnitTemplate.UnitModel.Kilobits
    attribute LOG_ELEM
    [MetaDataModel.MELODICMetadataSchema.ApplicationPlacementModel.IaaS.Processing.A
    ccelerator.FPGA.hasLogicalBlockNumber] : int 145000
  }
  location requirement PL [Locations.PL] $lo AvailSLO constraint ConstrModel.AvailConstr
  optimisation MetrModel.responseTimeUtility
}
metric type model MetrModel {
  composite metric context AvgAvailContext {
    metric MetricTemplateCamelModel.MetricTemplateModel.AverageAvailability
    grouping global
  }
}
constraint model ConstrModel {
  metric constraint AvailConstr : [ MetrModel.AvgAvailContext ] >= 0.99999
}

```

Fig. 7. Requirement, constraint, and metric models

The first snippet of RAN application's CAMEL 3.0 model (see Fig. 6) focuses on the polymorphic model, which involves the specification of the aforementioned components. This model includes the definition of a global set of requirements related to the components' location and the demanded number of resources. Further, four communications with their quality requirements are described while CU-CP has two configurations (a script-based with FPGA requirements and a serverless).

The next snippet (see Fig. 7) shows the requirement, metric type and constraint sub-models. The requirement model includes two requirements covering the quality of communication between DU and CU-CP as well as between DU and CU-UP. Each requirement specifies 2 attributes defining constraints on communication latency and throughput, annotated using MDS to point to the right network QoS data properties.

The requirement model also involves one resource requirement applied to all application components imposing a lower bound on RAM size. There is another resource requirement for all script-based component configurations imposing a lower bound on the number of cores. Another resource requirement covers lower bounds on logical element number and total memory for the required FPGA. All resource requirements are annotated with MDS elements. Finally, the requirement model specifies a requirement

demanding that all application components are located in Poland, an SLO related to a constraint on average application availability (described in the constraint sub-model) plus an optimization requirement over average response time.

The metric type model (not completely shown due to page number restrictions) re-uses availability-based metrics from a metric (template) model. Thus, it only specifies a composite metric context explicating the metric to be computed (average application availability) and the way measurements of the downstream metric (raw application availability) can be aggregated to compute it.

The above modelling clearly indicates that the combination of MDS and CAMEL enables to flexibly specify various requirement kinds over various attributes of related concepts like FPGAs, communication quality and CPUs. These concepts are not covered at the language level by CAMEL but only MDS. However, CAMEL has the flexibility to introduce requirements on those concepts at the model level.

The ability to select different deployment models from the polymorphic ones featured by the Morphemic platform and powered by CAMEL must be highlighted. Currently, the optimization objective is to minimize application's response time. Through a utility-based optimization approach, Morphemic will select a provider-agnostic deployment architecture with the script-based configuration for CU-CP that enables to utilize FPGAs. However, if the objective was to maximise the overall throughput, then the serverless configuration for CU-CP would have been selected. Thus, different optimization requirements lead to selecting different deployment architectures while the overall variability is covered and enabled by CAMEL.

6 Conclusions & Future Work

This work introduced novel modelling artefacts to support the complete modelling of polymorphic applications. Specifically, enhancements over two related modelling frameworks were discussed, CAMEL and MDS. A new CAMEL version was presented with additional artefacts that enable the complete specification of multi-cloud polymorphic applications, which can be deployed via MCMPs. The MDS schema, initially introduced as a formal vocabulary that properly covers the basic cloud resource and service types as well as multiple data management aspects, it was significantly extended to cover a richer set of resources. Now it includes HPC, edge and hardware-accelerated resources, plus network domain aspects. Last, a walkthrough of how application modelling works in a real 5G cloud-RAN application was provided.

The next steps of this work will involve a further evaluation and potential evolution of both the CAMEL language and its MDS vocabulary, through the validation of the extended modelling capabilities in terms of advanced, polymorphic-enabled scenarios, such as an e-BrainScience application for AI-driven analysis of clinical data and a computational fluid dynamics simulation deployed over HPC resources.

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